

Data as Culture

Description

Data as Culture is a program of the Open Data Institute; each year a different focus is selected that explores the relationship between arts and culture and open data. Since conception in 2012, the programme explores the wider implications of open data on culture and the culture of open data itself. In 2014, commissioned art projects were based on larger themes of surveillance, privacy and personal data and these themes have continued to play an important role in the ongoing work of the programme.

The Data as Culture initiative is intended for everyone, not just those invested in open data or the arts. Another part of its emphasis is on raising awareness of data and its ongoing presence in everyday life; it also encourages play, creative thinking and sharing of information and stories. One of the more curious pieces of art is a large scale knitting project that takes working hours within the digital economy and translates these into stitches within the knit piece of fabric being fabricated on a large knitting machine.

Social benefits

The intention of the Data as Culture programme is to raise awareness of the importance of data in everyday life, along with its pervasiveness in our cultural systems. Art commissions have included photography collections, participatory and immersive art experiences where the audience's physical actions become an immediate part of the art work. Many of the art installations are intended to provoke dialogue and encourage critical thinking.

Supporting links

<http://theodi.org/data-as-culture-2014>

Accessed 22 June 2016.

http://bit.ly/Data_Culture_Lighthouse

Accessed 22 June 2016.

<http://theodi.org/lunchtime-lectures/friday-lunchtime-lecture-data-as-culture-2014>

Accessed 22 June 2016.

<http://futureeverything.org/events/punchcard-economy>

Accessed 22 June 2016.